

Predictors of job satisfaction among IT graduates in offshore outsourced IT firms

Wickramasinghe, V.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V. (2009). Predictors of job satisfaction among IT graduates in offshore outsourced IT firms. Personnel Review, 38(4), 413-431.

This Version is available at: [doi.10.1108/00483480910956355](https://doi.org/10.1108/00483480910956355)

Abstract

Purpose – The study investigated the level of job satisfaction experienced by IT graduates fulltime employed in offshore outsourced IT firms (OOITF) in Sri Lanka; demographic characteristics that predict job satisfaction; perceptions towards IT jobs in OOITF; turnover and job search intentions.

Design/methodology/approach – The sample consisted of randomly selected 122 individuals who graduated in information technology field and fulltime employed in OOITF in Sri Lanka. Survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection.

Findings – The results indicate that gender and tenure are significant in job satisfaction measurement. Females are less satisfied with their jobs and feel loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF but wish to remain in the present workplace. IT graduates with longer tenure in the present workplace are less satisfied with their jobs, feel loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF and intend to leave the present workplace.

Originality/value – The majority of job satisfaction studies on IT personnel have been undertaken primarily in the West. The extent to which research findings of those studies could be generalized to South Asian offshore outsourcing context has not been widely tested.

Keyword(s): Gender; Information technology; Job satisfaction; Sri Lanka.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

There is a growing pervasiveness of information technology (IT) and growing tendency of Western countries to offshore outsource various IT work to other countries, especially to Asian developing countries with sufficient infrastructure and skilled human resource at a lower cost. As much of the studies have been carried out to understand the impact of this trend in terms of the economy, workforce and human resource management practices on the client western countries and consequently, Asian developing countries, where much IT work is being off-shored, make for an interesting area of study. In Asian countries, the phenomenal growth of the offshore outsourced IT sector has resulted in both extensive opportunities for IT personnel as well as increased stress in the workplace (Aziz, 2004). Both these factors have significant contribution to job satisfaction of IT personnel. However, the vast majority of job satisfaction studies on IT personnel have been undertaken primarily in the West, US in particular. The extent to which research findings of these countries could be generalized to South Asian offshore outsourcing context has not been widely tested. Though economic globalisation with outsourcing business environment impacts on work and employment, this is an area that has been underscored by researchers. Therefore, research on job satisfaction of IT personnel in offshore outsourced IT firms (OOITF) could be interesting, relevant and timely since there is an increasing interest in understanding IT work and workers from non-western cultures, especially those where significant offshore outsourced IT work is being done. Such analysis holds a number of implications for research on global IT, job satisfaction of IT personnel and women in IT.

Sri Lanka has been identified as one of the promising investment destinations in the Asia Pacific region for outsourcing of IT work since the early 1990s. Offshore outsourced IT firms operating in the country is increasing exponentially in contributing economic growth and lead

to a growth of a professional and technical middle class in Sri Lanka (Flecker and Huws, 2003). What is wanted by individuals from one country in terms of jobs could be different from what is wanted by individuals from another country (Anderson, 2002). As the available studies on job satisfaction of IT personnel took little account of differences between regions, from a practical standpoint it is vital to provide practitioners with key information that could enable them to make informed managerial decisions in a country that is considered as active and promising destination for offshore outsourced IT work in the Asian region. The paper specifically contributes to the literature on job satisfaction of IT personnel in several ways. First, there is a need to understand IT workforce issues more globally due to the increase in offshore outsourcing and the growth of IT firms in the South Asian developing countries, Sri Lanka in particular. Therefore, the study is situated in the widely interested area of global impact of IT personnel and IT in developing countries. Second, the paper is interdisciplinary in nature in that it explores the complex interrelationship between IT personnel and the organizational context. In doing so, the study focuses on OOITF themselves and the people who comprise them in the Sri Lankan context in which the encounter is embedded. Finally, the research setting is both progressive and international in nature as the paper explores a timely issue while maintaining an international perspective of the Sri Lankan context situated in a global environment.

For the study, job satisfaction is considered as a multidimensional construct consisting of overall or general job satisfaction that reflects one's overall feeling about the job and a variety of job satisfaction facets that reflects one's feelings toward different dimensions of work and work environment. By employing a quantitative methodological approach, the study investigated job satisfaction of individuals who graduated from universities in information technology field (IT graduates) and fulltime employed in OOITF in Sri Lanka. The specific

aims of the paper are to present and discuss empirical results from the survey on: the level of job satisfaction experienced by IT graduates fulltime employed in OOITF; the extent to which gender, age, and tenure predict job satisfaction; IT graduates' perceptions towards IT jobs in OOITF; their turnover and job search intentions. Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the paper briefly describes the Sri Lankan context related to the study and reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings.

Background of the study: Sri Lankan context

Economies around the world have become globally interdependent, introducing new forms of relationship between the economy, state and society. Sri Lanka, like other Asian countries, moves towards operating in a global market offering a liberal and dynamic business environment (Flecker and Huws, 2003). As Sri Lankan governments have identified IT services as a way to achieve competitive advantage in the global market, the government initiatives led to attract numerous offshore IT firms into the country.

When considering the big picture of the Sri Lankan workforce, the total working age population of the country was 16.9 million in 2005, of which 48.2 per cent were economically active - 67 per cent males and 33 per cent females. Sri Lanka is trying to promote gender equality in terms of increasing women's participation in the workforce and in terms of the range of jobs open to them. Of the economically active females, 22 per cent has an educational qualification of General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) or above, compared to a proportion of 13 per cent economically active males having the same level of education (Dept. of Census and Statistics, 2005). Therefore, one of the significant

observations in Sri Lanka is the increasing number of educated women entering into the economically active population and this trend is projected to continue.

When considering the data of the total IT workforce in the IT industry in Sri Lanka, the total employment at the end of 2004 was just slightly over 20,000. 46 per cent of the IT workforce possess a degree level qualification or above. Of the total estimated demand for a particular year, demand for IT graduates represents about 75 per cent. However, the annual supply of IT graduates is not sufficient to meet this demand (SLICTA, 2005). Of the IT workforce of the country, more than two third of the IT graduates are employed in IT supplier sector (SLICTA, 2005). When the available data of IT workforce in terms of gender is considered, female population is growing albeit slowly and it was 22 per cent of the total IT workforce at the end of 2004, which was only 17 per cent in 1998. Therefore, there is a need to better understand job satisfaction of workers, particularly using a gendered perspective.

The platform indeed for IT industry is better educated and trained employees; employers expect them to stay longer in a job. IT supplier sector suffers with the highest rate of turnover at 9.7 per cent while IT users come close with 9.1 per cent. It is also suggested the possibilities of better educated or trained IT personnel staying a short time period in a particular firm (SLICTA, 2005).

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Job satisfaction is a heavily researched area of inquiry. Systematic attempts to study job satisfaction date back to the 1930s (Hoppock, 1935). As a result of many decades of efforts by researchers, there appears to be a high level of agreement among scholars on the meaning of the construct of job satisfaction. Although there is no universal definition of the concept of

job satisfaction, it is conceptualised as a general attitude toward an object, the job (Cranny et al, 1992; Locke, 1976). Hoppcock (1935) defined job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that cause a person to say that he/she is satisfied with his/her job. Hoppcock (1935) further stated that a person may be satisfied with one aspect of his/her job and dissatisfied with another and that it is the responsibility of the individual to balance the specific satisfactions against the specific dissatisfactions and therefore arrive at a composite satisfaction with the job as a whole. Herzberg et al (1967) claimed that one of the major reasons for measuring job satisfaction is to answer the question, “what does the worker want from his/her job?” Locke (1976) defined job satisfaction as “a pleasurable or positive emotional state, resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences”. Therefore, job satisfaction is a fairly complex job-related attitudinal variable. It reveals an affective reaction to a job that results from a person's comparison of actual outcomes with those that are desired, anticipated or deserved. Further, job satisfaction is a multidimensional construct that consists of overall job satisfaction, as well as a variety of job satisfaction facets (Cranny et al, 1992). Overall job satisfaction describes a person's overall affective reaction to a set of work and work-related factors (Cranny et al, 1992). From the domain of IT personnel research, the most common and most important facets of job satisfaction are satisfaction with work content, pay, promotion, supervision, and co-workers (Igbaria and Guimaraes, 1993; Okpara, 2004; Sumner and Niederman, 2004).

Organizations in a given industry tend to take on similar norms and practices, resulting in a subset of work experiences that can be observed across various organizational contexts in a particular industry. However, evidence reveals that the level of job satisfaction experience by an individual could vary in terms of individual differences (Trauth, 2002). Of the individual differences that shape an individual's level of job satisfaction, demographic characteristics

cause variations in job satisfaction according to the demographic characteristics themselves, for instance gender (Gallivan, 2006). Therefore, there is a need to determine demographic characteristics that define job satisfaction of IT personnel to better understand and address issues in the IT industry thereby allowing suitable updates to be made to prevent the deterioration of job conditions in an organization. As there is a paucity of empirical research that addresses job satisfaction of IT personnel in OOITF in the South Asian context, as an initial attempt, it was decided to limit the study to investigate the ways in which individual differences in terms of age, gender and tenure shape individuals' level of job satisfaction.

Gender and job satisfaction

Met expectations are the extent to which an individual's initial expectations are met and those are a source of job satisfaction while unmet expectations may produce feelings of unfairness and inequity. Evidence reveals that IT personnel's ability to realize their met expectations is particularly important and that many women do not achieve their expectations, which creates morale and productivity issues (Sumner and Werner, 2001). On the other hand, equity theory suggests that individuals compare their contributions (e.g. skills, performance) and outcomes (e.g. pay, promotions, and supervision) to the contributions and outcomes of referent others (Greenberg, 1998). Individuals who feel that they have been "underpaid", or "not promoted", relative to others will be distressed and will attempt to resolve the inequity through behavioural or psychological changes (Okpara et al, 2005). In this regard, the literature gives evidence that women have been marginalized in promotion, salary raises, etc (Igbaria and Greenhaus, 1992). Further, they have been the object of "treatment discrimination", which translates into discrimination in compensation (Baroudi and Igbaria, 1995), prospects for promotion (Igbaria and Chidambaram, 1997), assignments to challenging tasks and access to

authority (Sumner and Niederman, 2004). One of the variables that is negatively affected by these experiences is job satisfaction.

Several studies indicated that there is a correlation between gender and job satisfaction, however no conclusive evidence has been reached with regard to the relative levels of job satisfaction among males and females (Igarria and Guimaraes, 1993; Sumner and Werner, 2001). Therefore, though numerous studies addressed the job satisfaction, much less is known about gender differences associated with job satisfaction and its related facets of IT personnel. Hence, for this Sri Lankan study, it is proposed that:

H1: Gender will have a significant impact on IT graduates job satisfaction, where female IT graduates will be less satisfied than their male counterparts in all the five facets of job satisfaction and in the overall job satisfaction.

Age and job satisfaction

Research evidence suggests that older IT personnel are less likely to quit compared to younger IT personnel (Igarria and Siegel, 1992). Kuo and Chen (2004) found that age was highly connected to job satisfaction of Taiwanese IT personnel while Sumner and Niederman (2004) found in US that prior job satisfaction and current job satisfaction did not correlate at a statistically significant level for age. Hence, research investigating the relationship between age and job satisfaction of IT personnel has produced mixed and generally inconclusive results. However, given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate a positive relationship between age and job satisfaction, it is therefore proposed that:

H2: Age will have a significant positive impact on IT graduates' job satisfaction.

Tenure and job satisfaction

Tenure is another variable that has attracted much attention in terms of its influence on job satisfaction. It is suggested that the length of service in a particular workplace could be used to estimate the level of job satisfaction of workers. The underlying assumption regarding tenure appears to be that dissatisfied individuals resign while satisfied ones stay with the organization (Oshagbemi, 2000). In terms of examining the same five facets of job satisfaction that have been considered for gender, some studies found tenure as a significant predictor of satisfaction with supervision and promotion, where tenure increased, satisfaction with supervision and promotion increased (Koustelios, 2001). Hence, the number of years spent in an organization is an age-related variable which has a direct relationship to job satisfaction. It can predict an affective response towards work (Bilgic, 1998). Therefore, for this study it is hypothesized:

H3: Longer tenure with the organization will have a significant positive impact on IT graduates' job satisfaction.

Perceptions towards IT jobs in OOITF

The studies that examined the work environment of contracting organizations identify two common features of these organizations (Budhwar et al, 2006; Pearce, 1993). On one hand, work in outsourcing environment is highly monitored and controlled by the management. On the other, these organizations consist of semi-professional empowered workers who work in a positive work environment. These empowered workers customize work to the needs of

customers and are more productive than routine workers (Batt and Appelbaum, 1995). Hence, work environment is bureaucratic but has elements associated with professional or knowledge-intensive settings appropriate to the customization of products and services. This is because, the management has to adopt a form of organization which reconciles the two conflicting principles, i.e. the standardization of processes and products aimed at lowering unit costs through scale and transaction economies and customization aimed at generating revenue by focusing on individual customer requirements (Frenkel *et al.*, 1999). Therefore, employees face a mixture of control and commitment strategies. For instance, the work environment is highly controlled and performance is closely monitored and strictly measured against targets. However, the employees are encouraged to take responsibility for both their team and their own performance (Budhwar et al, 2006). In this work environment, an important problem faced by the management is the high labour turnover (Budhwar et al, 2006; Frenkel *et al.*, 1999). Sri Lankan outsourcing sector is also suffering from high labour turnover (LIRNEasia, 2006). Other than the influences considered in five facets of job satisfaction, employees working in an outsourcing work environment leave due to working time and work-life balance related issues (LIRNEasia, 2006). The clients of the OOITF of Sri Lanka are in the Western developed world. Consequently, many OOITF operate during unconventional working hours to provide real time services to different time zones. The erratic working hours make normal socialization difficult, leading to alienation and identity crisis. Such concerns may be even more pronounced amongst females. This situation coupled with poor mass transport facilities after dark may discourage women from remaining in this industry (LIRNEasia, 2006). Therefore, for this study it is proposed that:

H4: Female IT graduates will feel more loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF than their male counterparts.

Consequences of job satisfaction

The identification of the level of job satisfaction and whether gender, age, and tenure do or do not explain significant amounts of variance in overall job satisfaction and its five facets, however, do not provide a complete picture. This should be done within the broader context considering antecedents to job satisfaction or consequences resulting from it. One of the consequences of job satisfaction is turnover intentions (Igbaria and Guimaraes, 1993; Sumner and Niederman, 2004).

A number of studies indicated that IT personnel exhibit little loyalty to their organizations and may well be tempted to leave a firm for anticipated higher rewards elsewhere as their skills are highly transferable across different firms and even different industries (Adya and Kaiser, 2005). Hence, organizations today find difficulties in attracting and retaining IT personnel.

It is also well documented in the Western context that the proportion of women in the IT field is small and shrinking despite the growing number of IT jobs (Trauth, 2002). While work-family balance plays an important role in shaping women's career decisions, research evidence suggests that work-related factors also play an important role in contributing to women's relatively higher turnover rates (Igbaria and Siegel, 1992; Sumner and Niederman, 2004). If attempts are made to identify the extent to which individuals who have successfully entered an organization are leaving along with job satisfaction, improvements could be made to help IT personnel to remain satisfied in their workplaces. Therefore, there is a need to understand the perceptions of IT personnel towards their work and work environment, especially in OOITF as such perceptions shape individuals' feeling of job satisfaction and

influence their decisions to stay or leave the IT industry. Therefore, for this Sri Lankan study, it is hypothesized:

H5: There would be significant differences in turnover intentions of IT graduates by age, gender and tenure.

The framework developed for the study is shown in Figure 1.

Take in Figure 1

Methodology

Sample selection and characteristics of the sample

For the study, the criterion laid by Sri Lanka ICT Association (SLICTA, 2005) that “an IT graduate is a graduate coming out of a degree programme at or above Bachelor’s degree level with at least 50 per cent of IT content”, was used in defining an IT graduate. “An IT graduate involved in producing IT related output as his/her primary job function in an OOITF belong to IT supplier sector as a fulltime employee” was used in defining an IT graduate in an OOITF.

It was decided to use the list of OOITF registered under Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI). BOI is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments (BOI, n.d.). Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 percent of their output (BOI, n.d.). Therefore, BOI

registered OOITF provide at least 90 per cent of their work for offshore client firms. There were 52 OOITF belong to IT supplier sector registered by the time of the survey. The sample selection was conducted in two stages. First, to select a sample of firms that fulfils the criteria set for the study, initial contacts were made over the telephone using the simple random sample method. Second, from those randomly selected IT firms, a random sample of IT graduates who fulfil the criteria set for the study was selected. Of the 300 self-administered questionnaires distributed, 128 respondents belong to 36 firms voluntarily responded within 3 weeks of initial questionnaire distribution. A total of 122 usable responses resulted in 41 per cent response rate. The demographics of the sample are shown in Table I and Appendix I.

Take in Table I

Method of data collection

The self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. The questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of 20 IT graduates who fit with the intended sample of the study to improve the reliability and face validity of the instrument. The inter-item correlation test was conducted. Test results for the overall job satisfaction and the five job satisfaction facets received standardized item alpha values higher than .7.

Measures

Five job satisfaction facets and overall job satisfaction were measured using sets of items on a five-point Likert-scale ranging from (1) “very dissatisfied” to (5) “very satisfied”. Overall job satisfaction measured using two items: “Generally speaking, I am very satisfied with this

job” and “I am generally satisfied with the kind of work I do” (Thatcher et al, 2002). Satisfaction with pay was measured using the item “I am very happy with the amount of money I make compared to what IT people get in private industry”. The degree of movement between different status levels in an organization was measured using the item “promotional opportunities are widely available” (Price and Mueller, 1986). Co-worker support was measured using the item “How satisfied are you with the people you talk to and work with on your job?” and supervisor support was measured using the item “How satisfied are you with the amount of support and guidance you receive from your supervisor?” (Goldstein and Rockart, 1984). To record perceptions towards IT jobs in OOITF a five point Likert scale used ranged from (1) “always feel loss of interest” to (5) “never feel loss of interest”. For turnover and job search intentions, five options were provided to indicate the most appropriate option. Respondents provided their age and tenure in the present workplace in years. Gender and marital status were recoded into two levels (eg: male 0, female 1).

Methods of data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS. Mean comparisons were used to determine whether there are significant differences in job satisfaction and attitudes towards IT jobs in OOITF by age, gender and tenure. Multiple regression was run using stepwise method of model selection. The stepwise method allows to identify the contribution of each demographic variable to R-square and the significance of the change in the value of R-square as a result of the inclusion of each additional variable in the equation (Bryman and Cramer, 2005). To determine how gender, age and tenure predict five facets of job satisfaction and the overall level of job satisfaction, a total of six multiple regression runs were performed with stepwise selection of variables (see- Bryman and Cramer, 2005). As turnover and job search intentions were measured as categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were used to analyse data.

Results

The level of job satisfaction

The results of the t-test for mean comparisons are presented in Table II. As predicted in H1 female IT graduates are less satisfied with all the five facets of job satisfaction (work content, promotion, supervision, pay, and co-worker) and overall job satisfaction than their male counterparts. These findings are contrary to previous studies that indicated females are more satisfied with their co-workers than their male counterparts (Igarria and Guimaraes 1993; Okpara et al, 2005); there are no gender differences for satisfaction with work, supervision, pay, and advancement opportunities (Igarria and Guimaraes, 1993); and there are no significant gender differences for overall job satisfaction (Igarria and Guimaraes, 1992; Baroudi and Igarria, 1995; Igarria and Chidambaram 1997; Kuo and Chen 2004). The findings of this study are in line with previous studies that indicated males are more satisfied with the nature of supervision that they receive (Okpara et al, 2005). By age, H2 is not statistically significant. By tenure, H3 is partially supported: the differences are significant only for work content ($p < .01$), promotion ($p < .05$), supervision ($p < .01$), and for the overall job satisfaction ($p < .01$).

Take in Table II

IT graduates' perceptions towards IT jobs in OOITF

Respondents were asked to indicate whether they feel loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF using a question on a five point Likert scale. Of the 122 respondents, 5 per cent indicated that they always feel loss of interest; 3 percent indicated that they most of the time feel loss of interest; 66 per cent indicated that they sometimes feel loss of interest; 25 per cent indicated that they ‘almost never’ feel loss of interest; and only 1 per cent indicated that they never feel loss of interest. The overall mean value obtained is 3.139 (SD= .07). The results of t-test for mean comparisons are presented in Table III. In the case of gender, mean differences are not significant. This does not support H4. In the case of age too mean differences are not significant. With regard to tenure, the difference is significant at .05 level. Results shown in Table III support the findings shown in Table II.

Take in Table III

Demographic predictors of job satisfaction

The results of the correlation analysis are shown in Table IV. As shown in Table IV, age is not significantly correlated with any of the job satisfaction facets or with the overall job satisfaction. It is evident that the tenure has significant negative relationship with satisfaction with work content, promotion, supervision, loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF, and with the overall job satisfaction.

Take in Table IV

Table V summarizes the significant results of the regression analysis. As shown in Table V, gender contributed significantly to satisfaction with work content ($p < 0.001$), promotion ($p < 0.001$), supervision ($p < 0.001$), and overall job satisfaction ($p < 0.01$). Satisfaction with pay or co-worker has not explained by any of the variables- age, gender or tenure.

Take in Table V

IT graduates' turnover and job search intentions

Table VI shows IT graduates' turnover and job search intentions. 58 per cent of the respondents do not intend to leave the present workplace. Though it was predicted in H5 that there would be significant differences in the intention to leave the present workplace by age, gender and tenure, the results of the Chi-square test indicated that intention to leave the present workplace is significant by gender and tenure. This finding is contrary to previous studies by Igbaria and Chidambaram (1997) and Baroudi and Igbaria (1995), which indicated that there were no significant gender differences for intentions to leave the job.

Take in Table VI

The results by gender and tenure are summarized in Table VII. Though females are less satisfied with their jobs and feel loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF they do not show high intentions to leave their present workplaces. By tenure, IT graduates with work experience of 5 years or above in the present workplace are less satisfied with their jobs, feel loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF and show high intentions to leave the present workplace.

Take in Table VII

Concluding remarks

The findings presented in this paper brought some much-needed diversity to the topic of how demographic variables shape job satisfaction of IT graduates engaged in OOITF in Sri Lanka. The findings suggest that individuals differ in the extent to which the job satisfies their needs, in terms of tenure and gender; the findings suggest the weakness of age as a reliable predictor.

The common understanding is that employees remain longer in their jobs if they experience a high level of satisfaction. The greater the satisfaction level, the longer the workers want to remain in their jobs. The reverse of this statement is also generally true (Oshagbemi, 2003). Further, it is said that longer service generally translates into additional protection and influences the possibilities of getting promotions, which directly increases job satisfaction. However, the results revealed that tenure in the present organization and job satisfaction are negatively related. Further, with longer tenure, IT graduates increasingly feel loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF and intend to leave present workplaces. Therefore, findings imply that job satisfaction of IT graduates who hop from one workplace to the other tends to be higher compared to those who remain with one employer. Furthermore, IT graduates who hop from one workplace to another may have a small number of years of experience in their present workplaces although they may have several years of service in IT industry as a whole. In this regard, during the preliminary investigations made by the author, it was revealed that the majority of OOITF that has mushroomed in the country has about two layers in the organizational hierarchy- top management and technical specialists; opportunities available for promotion are few and far between. To compensate this, firms offer attractive remuneration packages. Though in US Dollar terms cost of labour is considerably low with

compared to other countries in the region, in Sri Lankan Rupee terms, IT graduates in OOITF are paid relatively high salaries in the national context. Majority of training programmes provided are arranged based on project requirements; many firms use e-learning for continuous improvement purposes. In many instances firms use experienced IT personnel to work alongside juniors, where juniors improve their job related skills in a relatively short time. However, there are limits in having such opportunities for seniors. Therefore, it could be assumed that with longer tenure they increasingly feel loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF and intend to leave present workplaces.

The nature of the sample selected led to assume that males and females in the organisations do not drastically differ in having equal education, employment, and equal chances to apply skills to appropriate work challenges and so on. However, the results suggest that males and females differ in the extent to which the job satisfies their needs, where males scored high in all the facets of job satisfaction and the overall job satisfaction than their female counterparts. Further, females reported a high level of loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF while indicating a low level of intention to leave the present workplace. The characteristics of the sample have also indicated that females have longer tenure in the present work place, on average, than males. Therefore, this implies that the Sri Lankan female IT graduates remain in a given job because they have different expectations with regard to work. This is a potentially fascinating difference which could be fascinating to explore.

Managerial implications

When looking ahead to the results as its implications for the management of organizations in order to make better use of the opportunities that motivated and committed employees could

contribute to an organization, results provide better knowledge of the facets that give different levels of job satisfaction to individuals. The results revealed that job satisfaction facets do not give a similar level of satisfaction to both males and females. Both males and females showed highest satisfaction with co-worker. Females showed least satisfaction with promotion while males showed least satisfaction with pay. Further, the study revealed differences in the levels of job satisfaction between male and female IT graduates, where males scored high in all the facets of job satisfaction and the overall job satisfaction than their female counterparts. This lends support that more men than women enjoyed IT as a profession. When job satisfaction is seen as an emotional response resulting from the interaction of work, rewards and work values, the greater the perceived congruence between rewards and values, the greater the job satisfaction. Thus, an explanation to the different levels of job satisfaction reported for males and females is that females might have different expectations with regard to work.

The growth of the Sri Lankan OOITF has been accompanied by policy level interventions and national campaigns and programmes under a comprehensive framework. Sri Lankan organizations should increasingly realize the need of operating in a global market and the need of developing global strategies to locate themselves in a globally competitive environment. In competitively-challenged sectors, like IT, organizations need to develop a highly diverse workforce into motivated and efficient employees while coping with new problems of workforce retention. The way IT organizations manage their IT personnel is essentially manifested in their human resource management practices. For instance, increasing number of females entering into IT labour market implies that the differences in the level of expectations between males and females from the job have to be closed since work is an important aspect of individuals' lives and most individuals spend a large part of

their working lives at work. Therefore, the findings imply the need of introducing a number of adjustments and adaptations in the human resource management strategies and practices that take into account the discrepancies that exist according to the tenure and gender of employees.

Limitations and further research

This study was designed as a cross-sectional study employing quantitative methodology with a sample confined to IT graduates fulltime employed in OOITF. The size of the sample is also small compared to other studies conducted in the area of job satisfaction in the West. The findings of the study do not close the door for further investigations. Future studies could investigate how and why tenure in OOITF negatively affects job satisfaction of IT graduates employed in OOITF. Further, the sample of the research did not show large variations by the age of the respondents. Still findings suggest that there is a different relationship between job satisfaction and turnover and job search intentions for males and females, which could be explored. Though the findings suggest that females have low level of satisfaction with supervision, the data obtained for the study is not sufficient to further analyse whether respondents with same sex supervisors have higher satisfaction than respondents with different sex supervisors. Such an analysis could produce interesting results. Furthermore, though the results revealed that gender and tenure significantly correlate with job satisfaction, R^2 is small. Therefore, future studies could investigate other features- like social and cultural context within the organization and general society, and individual differences other than demographic characteristics such as self esteem, work motivation, job characteristics, role perceptions, etc. – to understand how these features get factored in. Finally, though

demographic variables are independently related to job satisfaction, future studies could investigate whether their interactions are also significant in job satisfaction measurement.

References

- Adya, M., Kaiser, K.M. (2005), "Early determinants of women in the IT workforce: a model of girls' career choices", *Information Technology & People*, Vol.18 No.3, pp. 230-59.
- Anderson, E.S. (2002), "Never the twain shall meet: exploring the differences between Japanese and Norwegian IS professionals", *Proceedings of the 2002 ACM SIG CPR Conference*, May 14-16, Kristiansand, Norway.
- Aziz, M. (2004), "Role stress among women in the Indian information technology sector", *Women in Management Review*, Vol.19 No.7, pp.356-63.
- Batt, R., Appelbaum, E. (1995) "Worker Participation in Diverse Settings: Does the Form Affect the Outcome, if so, who Benefits?", *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 33(3): 353-78.
- Baroudi, J.J. Igarria, M. (1995), "An examination of gender effects on career success of information system employees," *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 11 No. 3, pp.181-201.
- Bilgic, R. (1998), "The relationship between job satisfaction and personal characteristic of Turkish workers", *Journal of Psychology*, Vol. 132 pp.549-57.
- Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (n.d.), *Make It in Sri Lanka: business and investment environment*, Colombo: BOI.
- Bryman, A., Cramer, D. (2005). *Quantitative data analysis with SPSS 12 and 13: A guide for social scientists*, Routledge: London.
- Budhwar, P.S., Varma, A., Singh, V., Dhar, R. (2006), HRM systems of Indian call centres: an exploratory study, *International Journal of Human Resource Management* 17:5, 881-897.
- Cranny, C.J., Smith, P.C, Stone, E.F (1992), *Job satisfaction: how people feel about their jobs and how it affects their performance*, Lexington Books, New York, NY,.
- Department of Census and Statistics. (2005), *Bulletin of labour force statistics of Sri Lanka-August 2005*, Available <http://www.statistics.gov.lk>
- Flecker, J., Huws, U. (2003), *Asian emergence: the world's back office?* The Institute for Employment Studies, Brighton,.
- Frenkel, S., Korczynski, M., Shire, K., Tam, M. (1999) *On the Front Line: Organization of Work in the Information Economy*. New York: Cornell University Press.
- Gallivan, M.J. (2006), "Age, gender, and cognitive style differences in IS professionals", in Trauth, E. (Ed.), *Encyclopaedia of Gender & information technology*, Idea Group Publishing, Hershey, USA.
- Goldstein D.K., Rockart, J.F. (1984), An examination of work-related correlates of job satisfaction in programmer/analysts, *MIS Quarterly*, June, pp.103-115.
- Greenberg, J. (1988), "Equity and workplace status: a field experiment", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 73, pp 606-13.

- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., Synderman, B. (1967). *The motivation to work* (2nd ed.). New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Hoppcock, R. H. (1935). *Job satisfaction*. New York: Harper & Brothers.
- Igbaria, M., Chidambaram, L. (1997), "The Impact of Gender on Career Success of Information Systems Professionals: A Human-Capital Perspective," *Information Technology & People*, 10:1, 63-86.
- Igbaria, M., Greenhaus J.H., (1992), "Determinants of MIS employees' turnover intentions: a structural equation model", *Communication of the ACM*, Vol. 35 No 2, pp35-49.
- Igbaria, M., Guimaraes, T. (1993), "Antecedents and consequences of job satisfaction among information center employees," *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 9: 4, 1993, 145-174.
- Igbaria, M., Siegel, S.R. (1992), "The reasons for turnover of information systems personnel". *Information & Management*, Vol. 23 No 6, pp321-330.
- Koustelios, A.D. (2001), "Personal characteristics and job satisfaction of Greek teachers", *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol.15 No.7, pp. 354-58.
- Kuo, Y.F., Chen, L.S. (2004), "Individual demographic differences and job satisfaction among IT personnel: empirical study in Taiwan," *International Journal of Management*, Vol.21 No2, pp221-231.
- LIRNEAsia (2006), A baseline sector analysis of the business process outsourcing industry of Sri Lanka, Colombo, Sri Lanka (for more information: www.lirneasia.net).
- Locke, E.A. (1976), "The nature and consequences of job satisfaction", in Dunnette, M.D. (Eds), *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, Rand McNally, Chicago, IL, pp.1297-1349.
- Okpara, J.O. (2004), "Personal characteristics as predictors of job satisfaction an exploratory study of IT managers in a developing economy", *Information Technology & People*, Vol.17 No. 3, pp. 327-38.
- Okpara, J.O., Squillace, M., Erundu, E. A., (2005), "Gender differences and job satisfaction: a study of university teachers in the United States", *Women in Management Review*, Vol. 20 No.3, pp. 177-90.
- Oshagbemi, T. (2000), "Is length of service related to the level of job satisfaction?" *International Journal of Social Economics*, Vol. 27 No.3, pp. 213-26.
- Oshagbemi, T. (2003), "Personal correlates of job satisfaction: empirical evidence from UK universities", *International Journal of Social Economics*, Vol. 30 No.12, pp. 1210-32.
- Pearce, J. L. (1993). 'Toward an organizational behavior of contract laborers: their psychological involvement and effects on employee co-workers'. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36, 5, 1082– 1096.
- Price, J. L., Mueller, C. W. (1986). *Absenteeism and turnover of hospital employees*. Greenwich, CT:JAI Press.
- SLICTA. (2005), *Geared for growth: the improving stability of the Sri Lankan IT workforce-National IT workforce survey 2005*, SRI LANKA ICT ASSOCIATION, Colombo,.
- Sumner, M., Niederman, F. (2004), "The impact of gender differences on job satisfaction, job turnover, and career experiences of IS professionals". *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, Vol.44 No 2, pp29-39.

Sumner, M., Werner, K. (2001), The impact of gender differences on the career experiences of information systems professionals”, *Proceedings of the 2001 ACM SIG CPR Conference*, San Diego, USA.

Thatcher, J.B., Stepina, L.P., Boyle, R.J. (2002), “Turnover of information technology workers: examining empirically the influence of attitudes, job characteristics, and external markets”, *Journal of Management information Systems*, Vol. 19 No.3, pp.231-261.

Trauth, E. M. (2002), “Odd girl out: an individual differences perspective on women in the IT profession”, *Information Technology & People*, Vol.15 No.2, pp. 98-118.

Figure

Figure 1: Conceptual model

Tables

Table I: Demographics of the sample

	Total		Male		Female	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Age:						
< 30 yrs	82	67	52	67	30	68
≥ 30 yrs	40	33	26	33	14	32
Total	122	100	78	100	44	100
Marital status:						
Single	67	55	46	59	21	48
Married	55	45	32	41	23	52
Total	122	100	78	100	44	100
Tenure in the present workplace:						
< 5 yrs	77	63	57	73	20	45
≥ 5 yrs	45	37	21	27	24	55
Total	122	100	78	100	44	100

Table II: t-test for mean comparisons- job satisfaction facets and overall job satisfaction

	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig.(2 tailed)
Work content					
Age:				.705	.482
< 30 yrs	82	4.07	.76		
≥ 30 yrs	40	3.98	.62		
Gender:				3.504	.001***
Male	78	4.21	.65		
Female	44	3.75	.75		
Tenure in the present workplace:				2.911	.004**
< 5 yrs	77	4.18	.70		
≥ 5 yrs	45	3.80	.69		
Pay					
Age:				1.145	.254
< 30 yrs	82	3.71	.73		
≥ 30 yrs	40	3.55	.67		
Gender:				1.286	.201
Male	78	3.72	.68		
Female	44	3.55	.76		
Tenure in the present workplace:				.922	.358
< 5 yrs	77	3.70	.74		
≥ 5 yrs	45	3.58	.65		
Promotion					
Age:				.246	.806
< 30 yrs	82	3.71	.62		
≥ 30 yrs	40	3.68	.79		
Gender:				4.363	.000***
Male	78	3.88	.60		
Female	44	3.36	.68		
Tenure in the present workplace:				2.351	.020*
< 5 yrs	77	3.81	.56		
≥ 5 yrs	45	3.51	.81		
Supervision					
Age:				.566	.572
< 30 yrs	82	3.73	.74		
≥ 30 yrs	40	3.65	.77		
Gender:				3.432	.001***
Male	78	3.87	.63		
Female	44	3.41	.84		
Tenure in the present workplace:				2.497	.014**
< 5 yrs	77	3.83	.65		
≥ 5 yrs	45	3.49	.84		
Co-worker					

Age:				.658	.512
< 30 yrs	82	4.44	.70		
≥ 30 yrs	40	4.35	.71		
Gender:				1.911	.058*
Male	78	4.50	.59		
Female	44	4.25	.83		
Tenure in the present workplace:				1.191	.236
< 5 yrs	77	4.47	.57		
≥ 5 yrs	45	4.31	.87		
Overall job satisfaction					
Age:				.306	.761
< 30 yrs	82	3.79	.76		
≥ 30 yrs	40	3.75	.63		
Gender:				2.753	.007**
Male	78	3.91	.62		
Female	44	3.55	.82		
Tenure in the present workplace:				2.396	.018**
< 5 yrs	77	3.90	.66		
≥ 5 yrs	45	3.58	.78		

Note: * p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001.

Table III: t-test for mean comparisons- Loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF

	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig.(2- tailed)
Age:				1.24	.214
< 30 yrs	82	3.20	.79		
≥ 30 yrs	40	3.02	.47		
Gender:				1.64	.103
Male	78	3.21	.74		
Female	44	3.00	.60		
Tenure with the current workplace:				1.67	.097*
< 5 yrs	77	3.22	.80		
≥ 5 yrs	45	3.00	.47		

Note: * p<0.05

Table IV: Correlation analysis

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Gender	-								
2. Age	-.036	-							
3. Tenure	.275**	.458***	-						
4. Work content	-.305***	-.064	-.257**	-					
5. Pay	-.117	-.104	-.084	.140	-				
6. Promotion	-.370***	-.022	-.210*	.279**	.295**	-			
7. Supervision	-.299**	-.052	-.222*	.299**	.289**	.393***	-		
8. Co-Worker	-.172	-.060	-.108	.261**	.334***	.246**	.454***	-	
9. Loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF	-.148	-.068	-.151**	.102	.079	.157	.141	.050	-
10. Overall JS	-.244**	-.028	-.214*	.304**	.413***	.300**	.522**	.475***	.223**

Note: * p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001.

Table V: Summarized results - regression analysis

	β	R ² (adjusted)
Work content:		
Model 1: Gender	-.305***	.085
Model 2: Gender Tenure	-.253** -.187*	.110
Promotion: Gender	-.370***	.130
Supervision: Gender	-.299***	.082
Loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF: Tenure	-.265**	.074
Overall job satisfaction: Gender	-.244**	.052

Note: * p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001.

Table VI: Turnover and job search intentions

	Total sample		Intention to leave present workplace	Demographic characteristic											
	N	%		Age (N =122)				Gender (N =122)				Tenure (N =122)			
				< 30 yrs		≥ 30 yrs		Male		Female		< 5 yrs		≥ 5 yrs	
				N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not searching for a job and no intention to change the specialized field or the present workplace	18	15	No (N=71, 58%)	9	11	9	22	13	17	5	11	11	14	7	16
Intend to change the specialized IT field and move to another job but no intention to change the present workplace	53	43		38	47	15	38	28	36	25	58	42	54	11	24
Searching for a job in other organizations in Sri Lanka but no intention to change the specialized field	20	17	Yes (N=51, 42%)	14	17	6	15	15	19	5	11	9	12	11	24
Intend to change the specialized field and move to another job by changing the present workplace in Sri Lanka	14	11		10	12	4	10	10	13	4	9	2	3	12	27
Intend to migrate	17	14		11	13	6	15	12	15	5	11	13	17	4	9
Total	122	100	N=122, 100%	82	100	40	100	78	100	44	100	77	100	45	100
Summary: Intention to leave the present workplace by age, gender and tenure															
No (n=71)				47	57	24	60	41	53	30	68	53	69	18	40
Yes (n=51)				35	43	16	40	37	47	14	32	24	31	27	60
Total				82	100	40	100	78	100	44	100	77	100	45	100
Chi-square (2-tailed)				.778				.093*				.002**			

Note: * p<0.05, **p<0.01.

Table VII: Summary of results by gender and tenure

	Job satisfaction (Table II)	loss of interest in IT jobs in OOITF (Table III)	Turnover intention (Table VI)
Gender: Females	Low	High	Low
Tenure: \geq 5 yrs in the present workplace:	Low	High	High

Appendix

AI: Characteristics of the sample- work history

	Total		Working with the 1 st employer				IF “No [†] ” the current work place is:					
			Yes		No [†]		2 nd employer		3 rd employer		4 th employer	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Total Sample	122	100	87	71	35	29	20	57	7	20	8	23
Age:												
< 30 yrs	82	67	61	70	21	60	16	80	3	43	2	25
\geq 30 yrs	40	33	26	30	14	40	4	20	4	57	6	75
Total	122	100	87	100	35	100	20	100	7	100	8	100
Gender:												
Male	78	64	54	62	24	69	12	60	6	86	6	75
Female	44	36	33	38	11	31	8	40	1	14	2	25
Total	122	100	87	100	35	100	20	100	7	100	8	100
Tenure in the present workplace:												
< 5 yrs	77	63	51	59	26	74	15	75	5	71	6	75
\geq 5 yrs	45	37	36	41	9	26	5	25	2	29	2	25
Total	122	100	87	100	35	100	20	100	7	100	8	100

Note: [†] Captured only the situations of voluntarily leaving the previous workplace